

Deliverable 2.5: Sequential Decision Making

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1 Introduction

Sequential decision making is an essential concept in precision medicine, as it enables the individualization of treatment plans and the optimization of patient outcomes. One important application of sequential decision making is the use of machine learning (ML) techniques to analyze electronic health records (EHRs) for disease early prediction, patient phenotyping, and risk assessment.

EHRs contain a wealth of patient information, including demographic data, medical history, lab results, and treatment outcomes. Such dense information can be utilized by data-driven ML algorithms such as (un)supervised learning and reinforcement learning (RL) to extract valuable information and make predictions. And by analyzing this data over time, clinicians can make more informed treatment decisions and improve patient outcomes. For example, supervised learning algorithms can be used to predict the onset of different diseases by training on labeled EHR data of patients with or without the disease, and in both general ward and critical care settings [2, 21, 7], while unsupervised learning algorithms can be used to identify patterns in EHR data and group patients based on their characteristics, for discovering novel sub-phenotypes of certain diseases [20, 14]. Reinforcement learning is another important branch in the field of ML which can be used to optimize treatment decisions over time by learning from the outcomes of previous decisions. For example, RL can be used to optimize the dosing of medication or to decide when to switch to a different treatment [8, 12].

This report presents a case study that investigates the prediction of recovery chances from multiple organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS) in pediatric sepsis patients. Due to the nature of the project we have undertaken, we have opted to focus on the related issue of time-dependence in decision-making, which emphasizes the critical role of time-dependence in medical decisions. By accounting for the dynamic nature of patients' conditions and the varying time horizons for recovery predictions, this study offers valuable insights into how precision medicine can be augmented by integrating time-sensitive data and ML-based predictions. With enhanced predictions, clinicians can gain a deeper understanding of potential patient outcomes and adjust treatment plans accordingly, ultimately optimizing patient care and recovery.

2 Pediatric Sepsis and MODS

Sepsis is a life-threatening disease, which is defined as dysregulated host response to infection and the cause of millions of deaths all over the world every year [22, 17]. Sepsis disproportionately affects children as it occurs 22 times per 100,000 person-year in children, which translates to approximately 1.2 million cases per year [1]. Even in high income countries with low childhood mortality, sepsis and invasive infections contribute to 10 to 20% of childhood deaths, and account for one out of

four deaths in the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) [9, 10]. Moreover, children who survive sepsis may suffer from both short-term and long-term consequences, resulting in a lifelong burden to patients, families, and society [5, 19].

Multiple organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS), defined as dysfunction in two or more concurrent organ systems, has been associated with increased mortality and is a major cause of death in PICUs [13]. The pathophysiology of MODS involves a severe, systemic, uncontrolled inflammatory process that leads to dysfunction in multiple organ systems. Patients who exhibit MODS at the time of sepsis onset have a lower likelihood of recovery through treatment compared to patients without MODS. For those already in MODS when acquiring sepsis, it is vital to assess their chances of recovery to a mild state with zero or single organ dysfunction (Z/SOD), thereby providing clinicians with the opportunity to implement extra care and timely interventions for those who may otherwise not be likely to recover.

Objectives The objective of this study is to demonstrate that machine learning models, by incorporating physiological measurements and additional patient information, can accurately predict the likelihood of MODS recovery at various time horizons and track progression over time. Due to the project’s course, we shifted our focus to the related problem of time dependence in decision-making. By investigating the temporal aspects of MODS recovery prediction, this study offers valuable insights into the time-sensitive nature of medical decision-making in the context of pediatric sepsis and MODS. This study has the potential to enhance clinicians’ ability to make informed decisions and implement timely interventions, ultimately improving patient outcomes and recovery chances.

3 Database

Target Cohort The SPSS dataset includes the daily number of dysfunctioning organ systems (cardiovascular, respiratory, hepatic, renal, neurological, and hematological) according to the 2005 consensus definitions [6]. In patients with at least one organ dysfunction, daily values are available as long as an organ dysfunction was present up to six days after blood culture sampling, which we employed to calculate the outcome label of whether a patient with MODS on the blood culture sampling day (denoted as d_0) would recover to Z/SOD after six days (denoted as d_6). All organ dysfunction scores are based on laboratory, physiological, or clinical data captured in the database, and any missing value for the determination of organ dysfunction was set to normal. MODS is then defined as the presence of organ dysfunction in at least two different organ systems according to 2005 consensus definitions. The recovery from the state of MODS in the first week since sepsis onset is of high clinical relevance and has been previously studied already [18]. In total, the data set includes 4,498 daily records of 1,247 seven-day episodes from 1,149 patients (an individual patient can have more than one sepsis episode, and different episodes from the same patient were treated independently). The MODS recovery prediction model was developed based on the clinical records from the blood culture sampling day d_0 . Out of the 1,247 episodes, 991 were removed as they corresponded to patients who did not exhibit MODS or no record was available on d_0 , and hence no label could be assigned. Out of the remaining 256 episodes (from 240 patients), 50 deceased within seven days after d_0 , and 89 still suffered from MODS on d_6 . These two groups add up to 138 episodes, and they were assigned to the negative class (no recovery). The rest 118 recovered to a relatively mild state (zero or single organ dysfunction) on d_6 and were assigned to the positive class.

Types	Contents
Vital signs	Heart rate (highest), respiratory rate (highest), mean arterial pressure (lowest), systolic blood pressure (lowest), temperature (highest/lowest), oxygen saturation (lowest).
Laboratory tests	Lactate (highest), inspired oxygen fraction (highest), platelet count (lowest), white blood cell count (highest/lowest), lymphocyte cell count (lowest), total neutrophil cell count (lowest), total bilirubin (highest), serum creatinine (highest), alanine aminotransferase (highest), INR coagulation (highest), partial arterial CO_2 pressure (highest), partial arterial O_2 pressure (lowest), central capillary refill time (lowest).
Clinical scores	Organ failure scores (cardiovascular, respiratory, hepatic, renal, neurological, and hematological), Glasgow Coma Score (lowest).
Chronic condition information	Chronic disorder (neurological, cardiac, lung, urogenital, gastrointestinal, haematological or immunological, metabolic, malformation or genetic, malignancy, neonatal, surgical), dependence on technological assistance, history of transplant, total number of underlying chronic disorders.
Demographics	Age, sex

Table 1: Information extracted from the two databases involved in this study. The most abnormal value of each measurement was extracted within every 24 hours (indicated by highest and lowest). Except for the chronic condition indicators and sex being binary variables here, the rest features are numeric.

These 256 selected episodes from SPSS have a median age at sepsis onset of 6.58 months (IQR 0.30 - 53.54). 106 (41.4%) 7-day episodes occurred in neonates, 43 (16.8%) in previously healthy children, and 107 (41.8%) in children with comorbidity. 50 children deceased in the first seven days after sepsis onset with a median time to death of 1 day (IQR 0-2).

Feature Set The SPSS data set further comprises 22 physiology features (including vital signs such as heart rate, respiratory rate, systolic blood pressure, temperature; markers of inflammation such as white blood cell count, neutrophil count, lymphocyte count; markers of organ dysfunction or injury such as alanine aminotransferase, total bilirubin, creatinine), 17 organ failure scores (including the pediatric logistic organ dysfunction (PELOD-2) score [11], and the pediatric sequential organ failure assessment (pSOFA) score [16]), 16 indicators of complex chronic condition (including chronic neurological disorder, malformation or genetic disorder, and dependence on technological assistance [4]), 3 patient demographic features (including age, ethnicity, and sex), 34 infection characteristic indicators (including the site of infection and pathogen group). For physiology variables and scores, the dataset includes the most abnormal value per day for seven consecutive days starting and including when the blood culture was taken (d_0).

A total number of 44 features were selected with the help from the clinicians for the development of the machine learning model, which include vital signs, laboratory tests, demographic information, clinical scores, and chronic disorder conditions of the patients collected on the blood culture sampling day. Table 1 presents an overview of the extracted information from the two pediatric sepsis databases.

4 Methods

Prediction Model In the previous study [3], we already found out that the Random Forests (RF) model works well in terms of MODS recovery prediction one week in advance, which achieved an area under the receiver operating characteristic (AUROC) of 0.791 and an area under the precision-recall curve (AUPRC) of 0.736. We hence use the RF model for the investigation with varying prediction horizons in this task.

With respect to data pre-processing, we first imputed the missing fraction of inspired oxygen as 21% (i.e., atmospheric condition), and all numerical features in the raw data were standardized to zero mean and unit variance, and the remaining missing values were imputed with zero. For evaluation of the model, we adopted a cross-validation (CV) scheme owing to the relatively small number of patients available. In each run of the CV we randomly split the data into a training (80%) and test (20%) set, while stratified to preserve the specific positive label prevalence in the dataset. To make a fair comparison across different prediction horizons, we evaluated the relative AUPRC (AUPRC divided by positive class prevalence) from d_1 to d_6 , and we observed that the prevalence monotonically increased from 23.0% to 46.1%.

Model Interpretation In clinical practice, the interpretability of decision support provided by machine learning models is crucial for gaining the trust of healthcare professionals and enhancing the effectiveness of the models in real-world settings. To improve the clinical significance of our model and identify the most relevant features contributing to the predictions, we calculated SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values [15]. SHAP values offer a unified measure of feature importance that can interpret the output of various black-box machine learning models. They are based on the idea of evaluating the model using all possible combinations of features, both with and without the target feature, to measure the contribution of each feature to the prediction for a specific instance.

By calculating SHAP values for the physiological input variables with respect to the prediction task, we aim to identify the most critical aspects of a patient’s physiological state that contribute to their likelihood of achieving X -day MODS recovery. This approach allows us to determine risk factors among patient characteristics, which include not only their current physiological state but also permanent attributes such as demographics and complex chronic conditions.

5 Results

Prediction Performance As mentioned in the section above, we computed the relative AUPRC and AUROC from d_1 to d_6 , as shown in Figure 1. We can see that the RF models achieved satisfactory performance with all the AUROC over 75%. The relative AUPRC, which takes into account the positive class prevalence, is monotonically decreasing from d_1 . The decrease in performance over time is expected, which could be due to the increasing uncertainty and complexity of the patients’ conditions, as well as the greater variability in the data as the time horizon increases.

Risk Factors Our analysis of SHAP values across the six days revealed several key physiological variables that consistently emerged as the most important predictors of a patient’s recovery trajectory. The cardiovascular organ failure indicator and the respiratory organ failure indicator were frequently among the top contributors to the model’s predictions, highlighting the critical role

Figure 1: **Performance vs earliness** This figure depicts the relative area under the precision-recall curve (right) and the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (left) for the MODS recovery prediction from d_1 to d_6 .

of these organ systems in the recovery process. Additionally, variables related to blood pressure, oxygen saturation, and lactate levels also consistently appeared among the top 10 most important features, emphasizing their significance in monitoring a patient’s condition. Interestingly, patient age and the total number of chronic disorders appeared as important factors on specific days, suggesting that these demographic and medical history factors may also impact a patient’s recovery. Other noteworthy features included various measures of blood cell counts, creatine levels, respiratory and heart rates, and arterial CO_2 pressure.

6 Discussion

In this study, we demonstrated the potential of machine learning for predicting recovery trajectories in patients with multiple organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS). Our model exhibited outstanding performance, as evidenced by an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC) exceeding 75% for all six days, underscoring its capacity to offer valuable decision support in clinical practice. However, it is worth noting that the normalized area under the precision-recall curve (AUPRC) experienced a decline from 2.8 on day 1 to 1.6 on day 6. This decreasing performance over time is anticipated and could be attributed to the increased uncertainty and complexity of patients’ conditions, as well as the variability in the data as the time horizon expands.

By computing SHAP values, we identified the most influential features driving these predictions, thereby gaining insight into the time-dependent nature of MODS recovery. The primary features identified, including cardiovascular and respiratory organ failure indicators, blood pressure, oxygen saturation, and lactate levels, suggest the critical role these physiological variables play in the recovery process. Monitoring these variables enables clinicians to better evaluate a patient’s condition and tailor treatment plans accordingly. The time-dependent nature of the top features uncovered through our analysis carries significant clinical implications. As there are limited changes in the most important variables across the first six days, we assume that the temporal dynamics of a patient’s recovery process for MODS are limited. But due to the limitation of the dataset, longer prediction horizons like two or three weeks is not possible in this study.

From a clinical standpoint, the insights offered by our model can facilitate more targeted and effective interventions. For example, the persistent significance of cardiovascular and respiratory

Figure 2: SHAP values with respect to the prediction task for different horizons.

systems throughout the recovery process implies that these organ systems should be prioritized in patient management. Moreover, the prominence of patient demographics and medical history factors, such as age and the total number of chronic disorders, underlines the necessity for personalized treatment strategies that consider these elements.

The time-dependent nature of decision-making in this clinical context, in conjunction with the model's changing performance over time, emphasizes the potential utility of time-sensitive

data for optimizing patient care. Clinicians should remain cognizant of the fact that the model's ability to accurately predict recovery trajectories may be less reliable as the time horizon lengthens. Consequently, they should be prepared to adapt their treatment plans based on the evolving clinical context and the model's changing performance over time. By acknowledging the performance trends and considering the time-dependence of various factors, clinicians can make more informed decisions about when to intervene or adjust treatment plans in response to changes in a patient's condition. This approach allows for more effective management of patients with MODS, ultimately contributing to improved patient outcomes.

In conclusion, our machine learning model provides valuable insights into the recovery trajectories of patients with MODS, pinpointing key physiological variables across various time points. These findings could potentially inform clinical decision-making and contribute to enhanced patient outcomes. Further research is required to validate and refine our model, as well as to investigate other factors that may affect recovery, such as interventions or comorbidities.

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